

Association and Causation: Bradford Hill Approach to Aerotoxic Syndrome

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KEYWORDS

Bradford hill, aerotoxic syndrome, harm prevention, causality

ABBREVIATIONS

AS Aerotoxic syndrome

ABSTRACT

Causality in the tobacco and lung cancer controversy is briefly reviewed as background for Bradford Hill's seminal 1965 paper on "Environment and Disease: Association or Causation?" in which he identified nine features of evidence that can help us to identify a robust causal inference.¹

In applying these features to the Aerotoxic Syndrome (AS) evidence it is concluded that Bradford Hill would probably have assigned "fair" evidence for AS causality. Given the nature, extent, and seriousness of possible AS harm to crew and passengers, this strength of evidence is sufficient to take action to reduce the likelihood and extent of harm.

INTRODUCTION

"In occupational medicine our object is usually to take action" in order to prevent, as opposed to belatedly observe, harm.²

Sir Austin Bradford Hill, then Chief UK Medical Statistician, was addressing his fellow Occupational Physicians in early 1965 about the experiences and insights he had gained from the early years of the tobacco controversy. This controversy had broken out in 1950 when he and Richard Doll had produced preliminary

results from their study of British doctors which looked at their smoking habits and their lung cancer experiences. Their conclusion that they had found a "real association between carcinoma of the lung and smoking" was not immediately popular with the UK medical establishment, partly because most of the male doctors were then smokers.

However, by 1957, the UK Medical Research Council (MRC) had concluded, on the basis of additional positive evidence, that "a major part of the increase (in lung cancer) is associated with tobacco smoking, particularly in the form of cigarettes.....the most reasonable interpretation of this evidence is that the relationship is one of direct cause and effect".²

By 1964, the scientific debate was closed for relevantly informed and independent scientists when the US Surgeon General's Committee reviewed some 30 epidemiological studies, several positive animal studies, and some cell studies and had concluded that smoking caused cancer.

Note that both the MRC and the US Surgeon General reports considered association and causation as part of a continuum: "does the association have a causal significance?"³ This is to be determined by a judgement on the evidence. The dichotomous formulation by Bradford Hill, association or causation, has arguably encouraged sceptical scientists to withhold a verdict of causation until the evidence is very strong, by which time only some late harm can be prevented, instead of the earlier harm that action on reasonable evidence would have prevented.

The Bradford Hill approach to evidence and action

In Bradford Hill's still widely used seminal paper of 1965 which focuses on how we can move from an observed association to a robust causal inference, he identified nine "features" (often misnamed as "criteria") of the available, and often "ragged", evidence which, if present, could help justify a robust causal inference.⁴

Bradford Hill was careful to point out that if these

features of the evidence (Table 1) were absent, then that did not justify concluding that the agent being evaluated was not causing harm.

In other words, the features of the evidence were *asymmetrical*, a word he did not use despite making the conceptual point very explicit when discussing several of the features of the evidence.⁵

In coming to evaluate the current evidence on a completely new subject for this author (DG) i.e. that of AS,⁶ it will be helpful to apply the Bradford Hill approach to the question of causality, and adopt his concluding approach to harm prevention.

This last step was clearly articulated in the final section of his 1965 paper, the “Call to Action”. There he identified the need for case specific “*differential standards*” for the different *strengths of evidence* needed to justify actions that would reduce the likelihood and extent of harm.

He illustrated this point by giving three examples. For example, “*slight evidence*” he thought would justify banning a widely used pregnancy pill if the preliminary evidence included indications of serious birth defects. (He was writing as the thalidomide pregnancy pill and birth defects tragedy of 1962 was unfolding).

“*Fair evidence*” he thought would be needed to justify reducing or eliminating exposure to a *probable* carcinogenic oil at work, where the costs of acting prematurely, or wrongly, would be much greater than in the pregnancy pill example. However, “*very strong evidence*” would be needed to justify a government forcing “*people to burn a fuel in their homes that they do not like, or stop smoking the cigarettes and eating the fats and sugar that they do like*”. (Bradford Hill was way ahead of his time...).

He noted that in choosing the appropriate and case specific strength of evidence needed to justify action, the key consideration was the plausible *consequences of being wrong* in acting, or not acting, in a timely manner to prevent harm. In the case of the pregnancy pill ban:

*“If we are wrong in deducing causation from association then no great harm will have been done. The good lady and the pharmaceutical industry will doubtless survive”.*¹

Of course, much knowledge has been gained since 1965 but the Bradford Hill approach is still deemed by most relevantly informed scientists to be robust in the face of emerging evidence of harm.⁷⁻¹³

This is so even in the current contexts of the complexity, variability, uncertainty, and multi-causality that usually characterise health and environment controversies, such as the 34 case studies analyzed in “*Late Lessons from Early Warnings*” by the European Environment Agency.^{14,15}

There are many similarities between AS and the EEA hazard stories. For example, as with the AS case, “*no evidence of harm*” can be misinterpreted to mean “*evidence of no harm*”. This is usually not so because no, or very little, relevant, reliable, and long term research evidence is available, (as is still the case for AS) or because of the limitations on what *could* be known with existing scientific methods, under conditions of complexity, variability, and multi-causality.^{15,16}

Applying the Bradford Hill approach to Aerotoxic Syndrome

So, as to causality, what might Bradford Hill have concluded after applying his approach to the evidence available in 2017 on AS, were he to be around?

He would first have approached the evidence with this observation and question: “*The ‘cause’ of illness may be immediate and direct, it may be remote and indirect... But...the decisive question is; whether the frequency of the undesirable event B will be influenced by a change in the environmental feature A?*”.

As he was an assiduous student of history, Bradford Hill would first have noted that an informed warning about the potential hazard of AS came very early after the engineering innovation of replacing the cabin air taken from outside the aeroplane to taking it off the air intake to the engines:

“The observations of the flight crews constitute the first

Strength of association: case studies and clinical data indicate clear health impacts in significant proportions of exposed groups

Consistency: clinical data consistent with known toxic effects of organophosphates (OPs); and across varying aircraft types /countries

Specificity: AS is a syndrome (like AIDS; Multiple Chemical Sensitivity ; Occupational Asthma; Gulf War and Autism syndromes) and with common neurological/respiratory symptoms linked to oil leakage/pyrolysis products exposure in cabin air

Temporality: cabin air contamination precedes linked health effects

Biological gradient: more contaminant exposure often causes greater health effects; but low dose effects also apparent, suggesting non-linearity

Plausibility: known effects of Ops and other cabin air contaminants support a causal link

Coherence: animal/human data support a causal link

Experiment: health effects are often reversible after exposure cessation

Analogy: Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs); hot rubber fumes; welding fumes; traffic fumes, occupational asthma, leaded petrol, methyl mercury, OP pesticides, tobacco smoke have relevant features

Table 1 – The Bradford Hill Approach Applied to Aerotoxic Syndrome 2017

evidence of the existence of the problem. They have repeatedly reported presence of smoke and odor in the occupied compartments of the airplane".¹⁷

This early warning, like most of those in the 34 case studies analysed in the "Late Lessons from Early Warnings" reports,^{14,15} was not heeded, even after later warnings became available:

"...the Propulsion folks do not account or certify the bleed air quality....GE and RR engine specs do not mention bleed air quality when it comes to CO/CO₂ or hydrocarbon by-products.... With all diversions (about one every two weeks) and return-to-base events due

to haze in the cabin, (from failed fan and forward IPC bearing oil seals allowing oil by-products)..... I would have thought the FAA would have made the engine manufacturers address this by now".... "Bottom line is, I think we are looking for a tombstone before anyone with any horsepower is going to take interest."¹⁸

This preliminary, if largely anecdotal but informed evidence from inside the aircraft industry would certainly have stimulated Bradford Hill to quickly evaluate all of the available scientific and other evidence in order to help prevent, or minimise, harm to aircraft crews, pilots and passengers.

In contrast, regulatory authorities on AS seem to be following the pattern set in most of the case studies in the “Late Lessons” reports.^{14,15}

For example: “we can see nothing in this most recent or previous evidence that provides clear and consistent evidence of causal long-term health effects”.¹⁹

Depending on the economic and other interests at stake, the acceptance of causal evidence by regulatory authorities usually comes late, or very late, in the day.

In his review of the AS evidence, Bradford Hill would have been looking for the most likely interpretation of the evidence, guided by his questions: “What aspects of that association should we especially consider before deciding that the most likely interpretation of it is causation?” And “In what circumstances can we pass from this observed association to a verdict of causation?”

Bradford Hill would not have been impressed by the argument that if we do not know *how* A causes B then we should not accept that A *could* cause B.

“How such a change exerts that influence may call for a great deal of research. However, before deducing ‘causation’ and taking action we shall not invariably have to sit around awaiting the results of that research.”

And, for this feature of the evidence, Bradford Hill cautions us to note its asymmetric quality: “Biological plausibility depends on the knowledge of the day ... a feature of the evidence that we cannot demand”. He reminded us that an observed association “may be new to science, or medicine, and must not therefore be too readily dismissed as implausible or even impossible”.

In other words, if present, biological plausibility is a feature of evidence that can be useful in helping to infer causality, but if absent, we cannot infer non-causality with similar confidence.

Given what we now know about multi-causality and complexity in biological systems,²⁰ the asymmetry of all his features of evidence is now larger than in 1965.

Bradford Hill was similarly sanguine about the weight to put on the absence of statistical significance: “Too often I suspect we waste a great deal of time, we grasp the shadow and lose the substance...we weaken our capacity to interpret the data and to take reasonable decisions whatever the value of P.”

There have been many subsequent warnings about the misuse of statistical significance, but they too are often ignored.²¹

So, what would Bradford Hill have concluded from looking at the AS evidence in 2017?

Table 1 applies Bradford Hill’s nine features to the AS evidence available to this author in 2017.^{6,22}

This is not a *systematic review* of the AS evidence: such a review of the AS evidence is now clearly needed using recent methodologies.^{23,24}

This review is, however, a quick and tentative attempt to illustrate what interim conclusions Bradford Hill might have drawn from looking at the AS evidence available in 2017, where he to be around.

CONCLUSIONS

In my opinion, Bradford Hill would have most probably concluded from Table 1 that:

- the overall weight of evidence supports a causal link between aircraft cabin toxics contamination and health effects in some crew and passengers;
- the link is more likely than not i.e. at or around the “balance of probabilities” or “fair” strength of evidence;
- a high-quality case-control study is urgently needed;
- there needs to be an independent systematic review of the current AS evidence;
- pending this new research, action should now be taken to adequately monitor aircraft cabin air quality; and
- to remove hazardous contaminants (as I understand Boeing have now done with their new Dreamliner

aircraft which has reverted to taking air from outside the plane); and

- to adequately compensate the victims via a no-fault scheme (similar to that between the unions and British Nuclear Fuels for radiation induced cancer, 1985).

Perhaps the AS evidence is now somewhat similar to that on-air pollution and autism spectrum disorder in 2015?

*“Given the general consistency of findings across studies, and the exposure window of specific associations recently reported, the overall evidence for a causal association between air pollution and ASD is increasingly compelling”.*²⁵

It may also help, and would certainly be novel, if there were to be a “*Frequent Flyers Citizens Jury*” on AS using the tried and tested methods developed by the Danish and Canadian authorities.²⁶

Bradford Hill concluded his fine paper by reminding us that:

*“All scientific work is incomplete... that does not confer on us the freedom to ignore the knowledge we already have or to postpone the action that it appears to demand at the given time”*¹

Is this “freedom” to avoid using the available knowledge on AS being over-exploited by regulatory authorities and the aircraft industry? And, will it take a “tombstone” to shake their assertion that there is no “clear and consistent” evidence of harm from aircraft cabin air pollutants?

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